

An Operational Framework for Guiding Human Evaluation in Explainable and Trustworthy AI (Supplemental Material)

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Abstract

This supplemental material provides readers with information on the software developed and instructions on how to conduct a full XAI evaluation experiment, and how to replicate the results presented in the manuscript “An Operational Framework for Guiding Human Evaluation in Explainable and Trustworthy AI”, which was accepted for publication in the “Special Issue on AI Ethics and Trust: From Principles to Practice” in IEEE Intelligent Systems (ISSN: 1541-1672), IEEE Computer Society.

1 Developed Code

The open source code developed for this work (i.e., the XAI Questionnaire Generator¹ and the XAI Questionnaire Analyzer²) is available at Github. The specific questionnaire³ used in the experimental use case is also available.

1.1 The XAI Questionnaire Generation

This is a software developed in Python for generating an XAI questionnaire template (see Figures 1 and 2). It is distributed as a Jupyter notebook along with a Python script. The Python libraries *nbformat*⁴ and *ipywidgets*⁵ are required.

1.1.1 How to Run the Software

After downloading the software from the Github repository, open the terminal and move to the directory where the code is located. To run the notebook file, we suggest using the Jupyter Lab or the Jupyter notebook environments. They both open a web-based environment in your browser to edit and run the code. Double-click the file named “XAI.Questionnaire.Generator.ipynb” (listed on the left of the webpage) to open the template generator and use the “Run All Cells” option in the toolbar of the Jupyter environment to run it. An alternative to run the software is to click on each cell individually, following the order.

To generate the XAI questionnaire template with her/his requirements, the user must set first a preference for the given questions and then click the “Generate Template” button. The software

¹https://github.com/marcozenere/XAI_Survey_Generator

²https://github.com/marcozenere/XAI_Survey_Analyser

³https://github.com/marcozenere/XAI_Survey

⁴<https://nbformat.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁵<https://ipywidgets.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

creates in the same directory where it runs a folder with the XAI questionnaire template in the form of a Jupyter notebook, a readme file, and a text file for deploying the questionnaire in Binder.

Question 1

Qualitative Evaluation

- A qualitative evaluation typically consists of open-ended questions that gather no numerical data to achieve deeper insight into linguistic choices made by the system.

Quantitative Evaluation

- A quantitative evaluation, often viewed as scientifically objective and rational, typically consists of close-ended questions which gather numerical data. It is most well suited for testing hypotheses and statistical analysis.

If you need further details, please read:

- [Notions of explainability and evaluation approaches for explainable artificial intelligence](#): A systematic review that contributes to the body of knowledge by clustering all the scientific studies via a hierarchical system that classifies theories and notions related to the concept of explainability and the evaluation approaches for XAI methods.
- [Human evaluation of automatically generated text: Current trends and best practice guidelines](#): An overview of how (mostly intrinsic) human evaluation is currently conducted and a set of best practices grounded in the literature.

Considering the definitions provided, select the type of evaluation you would like to do in your XAI evaluation.

- Qualitative Evaluation
 Quantitative Evaluation

Question 2

In the context of XAI evaluation, you are likely to be interested in finding out whether automated explanations satisfy one or more of the following goals.

Transparency	Scrutability	Trust	Persuasiveness	Satisfaction
Allows to show the system's structural complexity/inside	Identification of a wrongly system	Increase of user's confidence in the system	Convince the user to perform an action	Increase the ease of use or enjoyment
Effectiveness	Efficiency	Education	Debugging	
Helping the user to make good decisions	Help the user to make decisions faster	Assisting the user to acquire new knowledge, generalize and learn	Enable the identification of system defects to the user	

Figure 1: Screenshot of Jupyter notebook implementation of the XAI questionnaire generator [1/2].

The selection of one or more explanation goals, after choosing the hypothesis to be empirically validated with your XAI evaluation, defines the type of task to carry out the desired empirical validation. Each task is aimed for a different goal, uses a specific evaluation method and provides survey participants with different information.

Task Type	Information given to the participant			Goal
	Input	Output	Explanation	
Verification	V	V	V	Explanation satisfaction
Forced Choice	V	V	V, ..., V	Explanation selection from multiple competing explanations
Forward Simulation	V	?	V	System's output prediction
Counterfactual Simulation	V, ?	V, V	V	Prediction of the input changes to obtain the alternative output

V = Information provided to participant
 ? = information inquired to participant

- In Verification tasks, participants are provided with an input, output, and explanation to ask them about their satisfaction with the explanation.
- In Forced Choice tasks, participants are provided with an input, output, and multiple explanations to ask them which one is the most suited.
- In Forward Simulation tasks, participants are provided with an input and an explanation to ask them to predict the system's output.
- In Counterfactual Simulation tasks, participants are provided with an input, output, alternative output (counterfactual) and an explanation to ask them to predict the input changes to obtain the alternative output.

If you need further details, please read:

- [A Taxonomy for Human Subject Evaluation of Black-box Explanations in XAI](#): A proposal of a taxonomy that provides guidance for researchers and practitioners on the design and execution of XAI evaluations.

Question 3

How many questions would you like to have in your questionnaire?

Figure 2: Screenshot of Jupyter notebook implementation of the XAI questionnaire generator [2/2].

1.2 The XAI Questionnaire Evaluation

The XAI questionnaire is a software developed in Python, distributed as a Jupyter notebook, for evaluating the real case scenario described in this paper. The questionnaire was constructed in agreement with the requirements of the designer, starting from the template generated by the “XAI questionnaire generator” tool. To customize a given template, the following libraries are the baseline required: *pandas*, *numpy*, *ipywidgets*, and *datetime*. To run the related XAI questionnaire, the following libraries are also required: *scipy*, *Ipython*, *random*, *urllib*, and *gsread*.

1.2.1 How to Run the Software

After generating the questionnaire template using the XAI questionnaire generator tool, move to the directory where the template is located using the terminal. Once again, we suggest to use the Jupyter Lab or the Jupyter notebook environments, which open a web-based environment in your browser to edit and run the code. Double-click the file named “Questionnaire_Template.ipynb” (listed on the left of the webpage) to open and run the questionnaire template.

1.2.2 Code Snippet Example

Next, there is the code snippets of the XAI questionnaire template. In detail, the code snippets highlight the functions that generate the code template for the “Welcome Section”, “Introduction Section”, “Example Section”, “Comprehension Section”, “Questionnaire Instructions Section”, “Questionnaire Questions Section” and “Questionnaire Participant Information Section” of the questionnaire. To entire code can be accessed in the Github repository.

```
1 def welcomeWebPage():
2     output.clear_output()
3     with output:
4         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h1>Questionnaire Title</h1>'''))
5         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>Welcome! This questionnaire aims to \
        evaluate "type of evaluation XXX\
        ". In this survey, you will be \
        asked to evaluate explanations in\
        terms of "evaluation methodology\
        YYY" following the instructions \
        outlined in the next screens.
6         This study is carried out by researchers from "University UUU". The \
        information that we collect is in\
        agreement with European Union's \
        General Data Protection \
        Regulation (<a href="https://eur-\
        lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj\
        ">GDPR</a>). In addition, this \
        research has been approved by the\
        related Ethics Committee. It is \
        meant for research purposes only \
        and based on non-personal or \
        anonymous data which is provided \
        during your voluntary \
        participation.</p>'''))
7         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>It is expected to take you about "time \
        MMM" minutes to complete the \
        survey. During that time, please,\
        focus only on the survey and \
        avoid any unnecessary \
        interruptions until it is \
        completed. If any break is needed\
        , take it between tasks.<br>
8         Should you have any questions regarding this survey, please address them to \
        'person PPP' (ppp@ppp.com), the \
```

```

9         survey and data manager, before \
starting.</p>''')
10     display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>By clicking the next button, you \
participate to the questionnaire \
and confirm that:<br>
11     <ul>
12         <li> You have reached the age of majority </li>
13         <li> You acknowledge that your participation is completely voluntary </\
li>
14         <li> You acknowledge that your anonymous responses may be used for \
research purposes in \
accordance with General Data \
Protection Regulation </li>
15     </ul>
16     </p>'''))
17     display(next_button)
display(output)

```

```

1 def introductionWebPage():
2
3     output.clear_output()
4     with output:
5         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h2>Introduction</h2>'''))
6         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>Description of the domain of interest</p>\
'''))
7         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h3>XAI Explanation Section</h3>'''))
8         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>Description of the XAI explanation</p>'''\
))
9     display(next_button)

```

```

1 def exampleWebPage():
2     output.clear_output()
3     with output:
4         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h2>Example</h2>'''))
5         # Provide an example in order to improve the user's understanding of the XAI\
explanation
6     display(next_button)

```

```

1 def comprehensionTestWebPage():
2     output.clear_output()
3     with output:
4         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h2>Comprehension Test</h2>'''))
5         # Test the user's mental model by asking some questions regarding the XAI \
explanation/domain of interest
6         display(comprehension_selection_example)
7         display(next_button)
8
9     # Datetime question displayed to the participant
10    comprehension_test_datetime.append(datetime.now())

```

```

1 def questionnaireInstructionWebPage():
2     output.clear_output()
3     with output:
4         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h2>Survey Instruction</h2>'''))
5         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>Provide details on how the survey will be\
conducted</p>'''))
6     display(next_button)
7
8     # Datetime comprehension test was completed by the participant
9     comprehension_test_datetime.append(datetime.now())

```

```

1 def questionWebPage():
2     output.clear_output()
3     with output:
4         question_number = questions_numbers.pop(0)
5         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h2>Question %s</h2>'''%(str(question_number\
6                                     + 1))))
7
8         # Input
9         display(widgets.HTML(value='''<p>Input of the sample</p>'''))
10
11        # Explanation
12        display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>Explanation of the system's output</p>'''\
13                ))
14
15        # Question
16        display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h3>Which is the output of the system given \
17                the input and the explanation?</\
18                h3>'''))
19
20        display(questions_selection[question_number])
21        display(next_button)
22
23        # Datetime question displayed to the participant
24        questions_datetime.append(datetime.now())

```

```

1 def questionnaireInstructionWebPage():
2     output.clear_output()
3     with output:
4         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h2>Survey Instruction</h2>'''))
5         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>Provide details on how the survey will be\
6                 conducted</p>'''))
7
8         display(next_button)
9
10        # Datetime comprehension test was completed by the participant
11        comprehension_test_datetime.append(datetime.now())

```

```

1 def participatInfoWebPage():
2     output.clear_output()
3     with output:
4         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h2>Information about the survey participant\
5                 </h2>'''))
6
7         display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>We would like to collect some information\
8                 about you to do a demographic \
9                 analysis of the participants in \
10                our questionnaire.</p>'''))
11
12        display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h3>Gender</h3>'''))
13        display(gender_selection)
14        display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h3>Age</h3>'''))
15        display(age_selection)
16        display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h3>Education</h3>'''))
17        display(education_selection)
18        display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<h3>English Level</h3>'''))
19        display(english_level_selection)
20        display(submit_button)
21        display(widgets.HTML(value = '''<p>NB: The sending of the answers could take\
22                a few seconds.</p>'''))

```

1.2.3 How to Deploy the XAI Questionnaire in Binder as Web Application

The questionnaire that we used in the use case described in this paper was converted into a web application with the *Voilà*⁶ library and deployed in Binder to share the application among the selected participants. The next instructions are based on information extracted from the Voilà website and allow readers to replicate our experiment with the given XAI questionnaire template, as follows:

- Create a “requirements.txt” file and lists all the libraries used in your code. This file contains the libraries needed to run the application in Binder. An example is provided with the template, but if you use other libraries in addition to the basic ones in your notebook, then they must be added to this file.
- Commit the up-to-date version of your questionnaire and make public the repository where your code is stored.
- Go to Binder and enter the URL of your Github repository in the “Github repository name or URL” section. In addition, in the “Path to a notebook file” section, click the dropdown menu with the default value “File”, select the “URL” option and insert the Voilà endpoint “voila/render/path/to/notebook.ipynb”.
- Click the “Launch” button. The service could take a few minutes to run the application if it is the first launch.

1.2.4 How to Fill in the XAI Questionnaire

To run the XAI questionnaire developed for our experiment, double-click on the file named “Survey_Application.ipynb” (listed on the left of the webpage) in either Jupyter Lab or Notebook environments. It is also possible to run it as a web application in Binder⁷.

1.3 The XAI Questionnaire Analysis

The XAI questionnaire analyzer is developed in Python for analyzing the data collected in user studies like the one presented in this paper. The software is distributed as a Jupyter notebook and HTML webpage. The HTML file is the front-end visualization of the Jupyter notebook output without the code parts. The HTML file requires a web browser to run, and it can be open with a double click on the file. The Jupyter notebook requires the following libraries to run: *gsread*, *pandas*, *scipy*, *urllib*, *Ipython*, *numpy*, *plotly*.

1.3.1 How to Run the Software

After downloading the software from the Github repository, open the terminal and move to the directory where the code is located. Then, double-click on the file “Survey_Questionnaire_Analyser.ipynb” (listed on the left of the webpage) to open and run it, either in Jupyter Lab or Notebook environments.

1.3.2 Code Snippet Example

Next, there is the code snippet of the XAI questionnaire analyser. In detail, the code snippet shows the computation of the participants’ prediction accuracy and the time taken to answer a question when a specific explanation was displayed. The “statistics” variable is a list that includes the total number of answers and the correct ones for each explanation presented. The “time taken” variable is a list that includes the time taken by each participant to answer a question when a specific explanation was shown. To see the entire code we refer to the link in the Github repository.

⁶<https://voila.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

⁷Binder Link, https://mybinder.org/v2/gh/marcozenere/XAI_Survey/main?urlpath=voila/2Frender/2FSurvey_Application.ipynb

```

1  # Retrieve the information (statistics and time taken) regarding data considered
2  statistics = questionStatistics(sample_number,5)
3  time_taken_1, time_taken_2 = questionTimeTaken(sample_number,5)
4
5  accuracy_1 = 0.0
6
7  # Participants' prediction accuracy computation with the respect to explanation \
8                                     1
9  # Statistics [0]: number of correct answers
10 # Statistics [1]: total number of answers
11 if statistics [0] > 0:
12     accuracy_1 = round((statistics [0] / statistics[1]),3)
13
14 tt1_mean = 0.0
15 tt1_median = 0.0
16 tt1_standard_deviation = 0.0
17
18 # Time taken by participants to answer the question when explanation 1 was \
19                                     presented
20
21 if len(time_taken_1) > 0:
22     tt1_mean = round(np.mean(time_taken_1),3)
23     tt1_median = round(np.median(time_taken_1),3)
24     tt1_standard_deviation = round(np.std(time_taken_1),3)

```

1.3.3 Results Example

Figures 3, 4 and 5 summarize the main reported results by the XAI Questionnaire Analyzer in the use case under consideration in the journal paper.

Figure 3: Comprehension section results.

Figure 4: Prediction Accuracy of the Participants.

1.4 XAI Questionnaire

Here we provide the screenshots of the XAI questionnaire as seen by the participants taking part in the study.

Figure 5: Time taken by the participants to answer the questions: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

1.4.1 Welcome Section

The welcome section summarises the questionnaire’s research goal, by whom the questionnaire is conducted and how to contact them, as well as GDPR information and the definition of the terms for participating in the evaluation. Figure 6 provides a screenshot of the Welcome Section in the XAI questionnaire developed.

Survey of the interpretability of decision trees

Welcome! This questionnaire aims to evaluate the interpretability of decision trees. In this survey, you will be asked to evaluate explanations in terms of decision tree interpretability following the instructions outlined in the next screens.

This study is carried out by researchers from Free University of Bolzano. The information that we collect is in agreement with European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In addition, this research has been approved by the related Ethics Committee. It is meant for research purposes only and based on non-personal or anonymous data which is provided during your voluntary participation.

It is expected to take you about 10 minutes to complete the survey. During that time, please, focus only on the survey and avoid any unnecessary interruptions until it is completed. If any break is needed, take it between tasks.

Should you have any questions regarding this survey, please address them to Marco Zenere (Marco.Zenere@stud-inf.unibz.it), the survey and data manager, before starting.

By clicking the next button, you participate to the questionnaire and confirm that:

- You have reached the age of majority
- You acknowledge that your participation is completely voluntary
- You acknowledge that your anonymous responses may be used for research purposes in accordance with General Data Protection Regulation

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Figure 6: Welcome Section Example

1.4.2 Introduction Section

The introduction section provides information on the domain of interest and the explanation generated by the AI system used for the evaluation. Figures 7 and 8 provide a screenshot of the Introduction Section in the XAI questionnaire developed.

1.4.3 Example Section

The example section provides an explained example by utilising a sample of the domain of interest. The aim is to help to revise the user’s mental model. Figure 9 provides a screenshot of the Example Section in the XAI questionnaire developed.

1.4.4 Comprehension Section

The comprehension section is for testing the user’s mental model. The evaluation is conducted using a task-based approach, checking the participant’s prediction accuracy. Figure 10 provides a screenshot of the Comprehension Section in the XAI questionnaire developed.

Introduction

The data used in this questionnaire is part of the wine dataset provided by UCI. These data are the results of a chemical analysis of wines grown in the same region in Italy but derived from three different cultivars. The analysis determined the quantities of 13 constituents found in each of the three types of wines.

- Alcohol
- Malic acid
- Ash
- Alkalinity of ash
- Magnesium
- Total phenols
- Flavanoids
- Nonflavanoid phenols
- Proanthocyanins
- Color intensity
- Hue
- OD280/OD315 of diluted wines
- Proline

This questionnaire considers decision tree representation in the form depicted below.

Figure 7: Introduction Section Example

This questionnaire considers decision tree representation in the form depicted below.

How to interpret the decision tree above?

A decision tree is a tree-like model that checks one attribute/feature at a time of a given instance to classify it in one of the classes of the domain of interest. A decision tree is made up of several levels and nodes. Each level is composed of one or more nodes, and the nodes correspond to the features of the domain of interest. Typically, a decision tree considers part of the available features, which correspond to those most relevant to correctly classifying an instance of the domain. Each node evaluates whether the value of the considered attribute is above a specific threshold. If the attribute value exceeds the threshold, the decision tree will test the attribute on the right path. Otherwise, it will test the one on the left path. In the decision tree representation of the following survey, the threshold of the root and each internal node is represented by the black triangle in the histogram graph, and the notations \leq and $>$ for the left path and right path respectively are valid for all the binary splits. To classify an instance of the domain of interest, the decision tree must reach one of the leaf nodes starting from the root node. A leaf node could be impure, so there could be a case where the leaf node contains multiple classes. The decision tree representation in the following survey highlights the composition of each leaf node and indicates the dominant class via pie charts.

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Figure 8: Introduction Section Example (continued)

1.4.5 Questionnaire Instructions Section

The questionnaire instructions section provides information on how the evaluation is conducted and the instructions to complete the questionnaire. Figure 11 provides a screenshot of the Questionnaire Instructions Section in the XAI questionnaire developed.

1.4.6 Questionnaire Questions Section

The questionnaire questions section consists of all the elements for the actual evaluation. Figures 12-13-14-15-16 provide a screenshot of the Questionnaire Questions Section in the XAI questionnaire developed.

Example

Considering we have a wine instance with the following features:

Alcohol	MalicAcid	Ash	AlcalinityOfAsh	Magnesium	TotalPhenols	flavanoids	NonflavanoidsPhenols	Proanthocyanins	ColorIntensity	Hue	OD280-OD315	Proline
13.2	1.78	2.14	11.2	100.0	2.65	2.76	0.26	1.28	4.38	1.05	3.4	1050.0

Considering the above decision tree representation and starting from the top level of the decision tree, the first feature to consider is the Proline. The value of the example is above the threshold of 760.0, so we need to take the right path of the decision tree and continue to go through the tree. The next feature we need to consider is Flavanoids, and the example has a value above the threshold of 2.17 and as before we need to take the right path of the decision tree and continue to go through the tree. The last feature to consider before the classification of the example is Magnesium. Our example has a value under the threshold of 135.50, and by taking the left path of the decision tree, we can conclude that the wine is of Class 1.

Before starting the survey, let's do a quick comprehension test to understand whether or not the concept is clear.

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Figure 9: Example Section Example

1.4.7 Questionnaire Participant Information Section

The questionnaire participant information section consists of questions to collect information about the participant for the demographic analysis. Figure 17 provides a screenshot of the Questionnaire Participant Information Section in the XAI questionnaire developed.

1.5 XAI Questionnaire Results

This chapter presents the results collected from the XAI questionnaire. It is organized into five sections, one for each question. Each section contains a table reporting the attributes of the dataset sample used in that question, and for both explanations, the statistics of participants' prediction accuracy and time taken by participants to answer that question. However, due to visualization issues, the table of each section does not contain the original names of the attributes. Instead, the notation used is the following: Alcohol (A0), Malic Acid (A1), Ash (A2), Alcalinity of Ash (A3), Magnesium (A4), Total Phenols (A5), Flavanoids (A6), Non Flavanoids Phenols (A7), Proanthocyanins (A8), Color Intensity (A9), Hue (A10), OD280-OD315 (A11), Proline (A12). In addition, explanations one and two in the following sections of this chapter refer to the 3-layers decision tree and 5-layers decision tree representations, shown in section 1.6.

1.5.1 Comprehension Questions

The "Comprehension" section aimed to measure the participants' mental model through two questions, considering a task-based approach constructed to ask the participants of the evaluation to guess the class to which the given sample of the dataset belongs. The questions proposed to the participants of the evaluation were:

- **Q1:** Which class corresponds to the wine with the following features?
- **Q2:** Which of the following features/attributes did you consider for the classification?

Figure 18 highlights that 91.7% of the participants answered the first question correctly, and all of them answered correctly to Q2. Considering these results, we can conclude that the information provided through initial instructions was sufficiently good to create a good user mental model.

Comprehension Test

Considering we have a wine with the following features:

Alcohol	MalicAcid	Ash	AlcalinityOfAsh	Magnesium	TotalPhenols	flavanols	NonflavanolsPhenols	Proanthocyanins	ColorIntensity	Hue	OD280-OD315	Proline
12.42	2.55	2.27	22.0	90.0	1.68	1.84	0.66	1.42	2.7	0.86	3.3	315.0

Let's consider the decision tree representation below.

Which class correspond the wine with the following features?

- Class 1
- Class 2
- Class 3

Which of the following features/attributes did you consider for the classification?

- Proline, OD280/OD315, and Flavanols
- Proline, OD280/OD315, and Hue
- Proline, Flavanols, and Magnesium
- Proline, Flavanols, and Hue

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Figure 10: Comprehension Section Example

Survey Instruction

The questionnaire is composed by five task-based questions, and each of them is made of the following elements:

- The features of a wine instance.
- A decision tree representation of the the domain of interest.
- A question asking for the correct classification of the wine instance, considering the decision tree representation of the domain of interest.

Once the questions are completed, to conclude the questionnaire, we will ask you to provide us with some information about yourself to do a demographic analysis of the participants of this questionnaire.

You can start the questionnaire

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Figure 11: Questionnaire Instructions Section Example

1.5.2 Questionnaire Questions

The “Questionnaire Questions” section was the core of the experiment that aimed to achieve the research goal set for the experiment. Recalling the research goal set, the experiment wanted to assess two explanations in terms of interpretability.

Question 1

The sample used in question 1 is from row 0 of the dataset, and it has the following attributes:

A0	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12
14.23	1.71	2.43	15.6	127.0	2.8	3.06	0.28	2.29	5.64	1.04	3.92	1065.0

Table 1: Attributes of the dataset sample in row 0.

The correct classification of the sample of row 0 is “Class 1”. Figure 19 highlights a higher participants’ prediction accuracy when explanation two was proposed. Still, as depicted in figure 20, the participants took more time to respond when explanation two was presented. In detail, the mean, median, and standard deviation of the time (in seconds) taken by the participants of the experiment to answer

Question 1

Considering a wine instance with the following features:

Alcohol	MalicAcid	Ash	AlcalinityOfAsh	Magnesium	TotalPhenols	flavanoids	NonflavanoidsPhenols	Proanthocyanins	Colorintensity	Hue	OD280-OD315	Proline
13.74	1.67	2.25		16.4	118.0	2.6	2.9	0.21	1.62	5.85	0.92	3.2 1060.0

Let's consider the following decision tree representation:

Which class correspond the wine with the following features?

- Class 1
- Class 2
- Class 3

Next

Figure 12: Questionnaire Instructions Section Example

question one when explanations one and two were displayed were:

- **Explanation 1:** Mean = 24.334 s, Median = 20.324 s, Standard Deviation = 9.460 s.
- **Explanation 2:** Mean = 54.116 s, Median = 39.630 s, Standard Deviation = 37.082 s.

Question 2

The sample used in question 2 is from row 58 of the dataset, and it has the following attributes:

A0	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12
12.37	1.13	2.16	19.0	87.0	3.5	3.1	0.19	1.87	4.45	1.22	2.87	420.0

Table 2: Attributes of the dataset sample in row 58.

The correct classification of the sample of row 58 is “Class 2”. Figure 21 highlights a higher participants’ prediction accuracy when explanation two was proposed. Still, as depicted in figure 22, the participants took more time to respond when explanation two was presented. In detail, the mean, median, and standard deviation of the time (in seconds) taken by the participants of the experiment to answer question two when explanations one and two were displayed were:

- **Explanation 1:** Mean = 30.017 s, Median = 21.450 s, Standard Deviation = 19.864 s.
- **Explanation 2:** Mean = 57.928 s, Median = 29.056 s, Standard Deviation = 59.660 s.

Question 3

The sample used in question 3 is from row 156 of the dataset, and it has the following attributes:

The correct classification of the sample of row 156 is “Class 3”. Figure 23 highlights the same participants’ prediction accuracy when explanations one and two were proposed. A similar phenomenon can be found with the time taken by the participants to answer the question, as depicted in figure 24. In

Question 2

Considering a wine instance with the following features:

Alcohol	MalicAcid	Ash	AlcalinityOfAsh	Magnesium	TotalPhenols	flavanoids	NonflavanoidsPhenols	Proanthocyanins	ColorIntensity	Hue	OD280-OD315	Proline
13.4	3.91	2.48	23.0	102.0	1.8	0.75	0.43	1.41	7.3	0.7	1.56	750.0

Let's consider the following decision tree representation:

Which class correspond the wine with the following features?

- Class 1
- Class 2
- Class 3

Next

Figure 13: Questionnaire Instructions Section Example 2

A0	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12
13.71	5.65	2.45	20.5	95.0	1.68	0.61	0.52	1.06	7.7	0.64	1.74	740.0

Table 3: Attributes of the dataset sample in row 156.

detail, the mean, median, and standard deviation of the time (in seconds) taken by the participants of the experiment to answer question three when explanations one and two were displayed were:

- **Explanation 1:** Mean = 29.853 s, Median = 30.653 s, Standard Deviation = 14.991 s.
- **Explanation 2:** Mean = 30.027 s, Median = 31.159 s, Standard Deviation = 5.945 s.

Question 4

The sample used in question 4 is from row 164 of the dataset, and it has the following attributes:

A0	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12
13.74	1.67	2.25	16.4	118.0	2.6	2.9	0.21	1.62	5.85	0.92	3.2	1060.0

Table 4: Attributes of the dataset sample in row 164.

The correct classification of the sample of row 164 is “Class 1”. Figure 25 highlights a higher participants’ prediction accuracy when explanation two was proposed. However, as depicted in figure 26, the participants took a similar amount of time to answer question four when explanations one and two were presented. In detail, the mean, median, and standard deviation of the time (in seconds) taken by the participants of the experiment to answer question four when explanations one and two were displayed were:

- **Explanation 1:** Mean = 39.451 s, Median = 25.490 s, Standard Deviation = 26.716 s.
- **Explanation 2:** Mean = 27.340 s, Median = 25.816 s, Standard Deviation = 11.376 s.

Question 5

Question 4

Considering a wine instance with the following features:

Alcohol	MalicAcid	Ash	AlcalinityOfAsh	Magnesium	TotalPhenols	flavanoids	NonflavanoidsPhenols	Proanthocyanins	ColorIntensity	Hue	OD280-OD315	Proline	
14.23	1.71	2.43		15.6	127.0	2.8	3.06	0.28	2.29	5.64	1.04	3.92	1065.0

Let's consider the following decision tree representation:

Which class correspond the wine with the following features?

- Class 1
- Class 2
- Class 3

Next

Next

Figure 15: Questionnaire Instructions Section Example 4

Question 5

Considering a wine instance with the following features:

Alcohol	MalicAcid	Ash	AlcalinityOfAsh	Magnesium	TotalPhenols	flavanoids	NonflavanoidsPhenols	Proanthocyanins	ColorIntensity	Hue	OD280-OD315	Proline	
12.37	1.13	2.16		19.0	87.0	3.5	3.1	0.19	1.87	4.45	1.22	2.87	420.0

Let's consider the following decision tree representation:

Which class correspond the wine with the following features?

- Class 1
- Class 2
- Class 3

Next

Figure 16: Questionnaire Instructions Section Example 5

Information about the survey participant

We would like to collect some information about you to do a demographic analysis of the participants in our questionnaire.

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Age

- 18-20
- 21-29
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60 or older

Education

- Less than high school degree
- High school degree or equivalent
- Undergraduate
- Graduate

English Level

- Beginner (A1)
- Elementary (A2)
- Lower Intermediate (B1)
- Upper Intermediate (B2)
- Advanced (C1)
- Proficient (C2)

Submit

NB: The sending of the answers could take a few seconds.

Figure 17: Questionnaire Participant Information Section Example

Q1 & Q2 Results

Figure 18: Comprehension section results.

Prediction Accuracy of the Participants: Explanation 1 vs Explanation 2

Figure 19: Prediction accuracy of the participants in question 1: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Time Taken by the Participants to Answer the Question: Explanation 1 vs Explanation 2

Figure 20: Time taken by participants to answer the question 1: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Prediction Accuracy of the Participants: Explanation 1 vs Explanation 2

Figure 21: Prediction accuracy of the participants in question 2: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Time Taken by the Participants to Answer the Question: Explanation 1 vs Explanation 2

Figure 22: Time taken by participants to answer the question 2: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Prediction Accuracy of the Participants: Explanation 1 vs Explanation 2

Figure 23: Prediction accuracy of the participants in question 3: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Figure 24: Time taken by participants to answer the question 3: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Figure 25: Prediction accuracy of the participants in question 4: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Figure 26: Time taken by participants to answer the question 4: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Figure 27: Prediction accuracy of the participants in question 5: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Time Taken by the Participants to Answer the Question: Explanation 1 vs Explanation 2

Figure 28: Time taken by participants to answer the question 5: Explanation 1 VS Explanation 2.

Participants Gender

Figure 29: Participants Gender.

Participants Age

Figure 30: Participants Age.

Participants Education Level

Figure 31: Participants Education Level.

Participants English Level

Figure 32: Participants English Level.

1.6 Decision trees used in the XAI Questionnaire

Figures 33 and 34 show the decision trees used in the XAI Questionnaire.

Figure 33: Dtreviz decision tree representation of the dataset used in the XAI evaluation (3-layers).

Figure 34: Dtreviz decision tree representation of the dataset used in the XAI evaluation (5-layers).

1.7 User satisfaction with the operational framework

This section includes code snippets of the Python notebook that we used to carry out the analysis of answers in a user study aimed for evaluating the satisfaction of users with the provided operational framework.

Each section in the notebook explains what information was provided to the survey participants and highlight the results obtained.

We begin with importing libraries and loading data.

```
1 # Libraries Import
2 import pandas as pd
3 from scipy.io import arff
4 import csv
5 from IPython.display import SVG, Markdown, HTML, display
6 import numpy as np
7 import plotly.graph_objects as go
8 from plotly.subplots import make_subplots
9 import warnings
10 warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
```

```
1 # Dataset Load
2 dataWine = arff.loadarff("./WINE.txt.arff")
3 dataset = pd.DataFrame(dataWine[0])
```

```
1 # Function to convert the "Class" column of the dataset into more readable values
2 def labelConversion(label):
3     if label == b'1':
4         return 'Class 1'
5     elif label == b'2':
6         return 'Class 2'
7     else:
8         return 'Class 3'
9
10 dataset['Class'] = dataset['Class'].apply(lambda x: labelConversion(x))
```

```
1 # Load csv file
2 filename = 'SurveyAnswers-Study2.csv'
3 with open(filename, newline='') as f:
4     reader = csv.reader(f)
5     rows = []
6     try:
7         for row in reader:
8             #print(row)
9             rows.append(row)
10    except csv.Error as e:
11        print('file {}, line {}: {}'.format(filename, reader.line_num, e))
12
13 labels = rows.pop(0)
14 data = pd.DataFrame(data = rows, columns = labels)
15 nr = len(rows)
16 print("The number of participants is {}".format(str(nr)))
17 data.head(nr)
```

We included a sample of 47 participants who took part in a series of three independent sessions (each session took 1 hour). The target audience was made up of students who were enrolled in three thematic training courses related to Explainable and Trustworthy AI:

- Training Course 1: “Fundamentals of (and tools for) Explainable and Trustworthy AI” (Technological Institute of Galicia, Spain) (14 participants).
- Training Course 2: “Explainable and Trustworthy AI” (University of Lille, France) (14 participants).
- Training Course 3: “Explainable and Trustworthy AI” (University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain) (19 participants).

Accordingly, participants are deemed as AI researchers with technical background. They first answered to the comprehension test (see further details in [1.4.4](#)).

```

1 # Retrieving the example in row 1 from the dataset
2 comprehension_test_sample = dataset.iloc[96][:-1].to_frame()
3 comprehension_test_sample.rename(columns = {comprehension_test_sample.columns[0]:''} \
4                                     , inplace = True)
5
6 comprehension_test_sample.transpose()
7
8 comprehension_test_answers = data['Comprehension-Test Answers'].to_list()
9
10 # Computation of the participants' accuracy in answers given in the Comprehension \
11     Test section
12
13 incorrect = []
14 comprehension_test_correct_answers_q1 = 0
15 comprehension_test_wrong_answers_q1 = 0
16 comprehension_test_correct_answers_q2 = 0
17 comprehension_test_wrong_answers_q2 = 0
18
19 cont = 0
20 for cell_1 in comprehension_test_answers:
21     user_answers = cell_1.split(',')
22     warn = False
23
24     if user_answers[0] == '2':
25         comprehension_test_correct_answers_q1 += 1
26     else:
27         comprehension_test_wrong_answers_q1 += 1
28         warn = True
29
30     if user_answers[1] == '1':
31         comprehension_test_correct_answers_q2 += 1
32     else:
33         comprehension_test_wrong_answers_q2 += 1
34         warn = True
35
36     if (warn):
37         incorrect.insert(0, cont)
38
39     cont = cont + 1
40
41 print("Cases to remove because users failed the Comprehension Test: ")
42 print(incorrect)
43 for c in incorrect:
44     data = data.drop(data.index[c])
45
46 nr = len(data)
47 print("The number of valid participants is {}".format(str(nr)))
48 data.head(nr)
49
50 q1_accuracy = round(comprehension_test_correct_answers_q1 / ( \
51                     comprehension_test_correct_answers_q1 + \
52                     comprehension_test_wrong_answers_q1),3)
53 q2_accuracy = round(comprehension_test_correct_answers_q2 / ( \

```

```

48                                     comprehension_test_correct_answers_q2 + \
49                                     comprehension_test_wrong_answers_q2),3)
49 # Pie chart visualization of the Comprehension Test section results
50 comprehension_test_fig = make_subplots(rows=1, cols=2, specs=[[{"type": "pie"}, {"\
51                                     type": "pie"}]])
52
53 comprehension_test_fig.add_trace(go.Pie(
54     values=[comprehension_test_correct_answers_q1, \
55                                     comprehension_test_wrong_answers_q1]\
56     ,
57     labels=["Correct Answers", "Uncorrect Answers"],
58     hole=.5,
59     name="Q1"),
60     row=1, col=1)
61
62 comprehension_test_fig.add_trace(go.Pie(
63     values=[comprehension_test_correct_answers_q2, \
64                                     comprehension_test_wrong_answers_q2]\
65     ,
66     labels=["Correct Answers", "Uncorrect Answers"],
67     hole=.5,
68     name="Q2"),
69     row=1, col=2)
70
71 comprehension_test_fig.update_layout(height=400, width=1000, title_text="Q1 & Q2 \
72                                     Results")

```


Figure 35: Results of the comprehension test in the second user study.

Only those 38 participants who passed the comprehension test went to the next stage in which they had to answer four task-oriented questions (a subset of those considered in the first study; with two questions related to Explanation 1 and two questions related to Explanation 2). Interestingly, most participants were able to accomplish well the required tasks no matter the complexity of the given explanation (see Fig. 36). This fact met our expectations because we deal with decision trees as explainers, and they are worldwide recognized as transparent white-box AI models.

```

1 # Function for computing the statistics of the 'Questions' section
2 # The function retrieves all the information for computing the participants' \
    accuracy on answering the questions
3 def questionStatistics(sample_number, number_of_questions):
4     representation_1_occurrences = 0
5     representation_1_correct_answers = 0
6     representation_2_occurrences = 0
7     representation_2_correct_answers = 0
8
9     for i in range(1, number_of_questions + 1):
10        string_1 = 'Q%s Answer'%i
11        dataq = data
12        for row in dataq[string_1].to_list():
13            elements = row.split(', ')
14
15            if elements[0] == str(sample_number) and elements[3] == '1':
16                if elements[1] == elements[2]:
17                    representation_1_correct_answers += 1
18                representation_1_occurrences += 1
19            elif elements[0] == str(sample_number) and elements[3] == '2':
20                if elements[1] == elements[2]:
21                    representation_2_correct_answers += 1
22                representation_2_occurrences += 1
23
24    return (representation_1_correct_answers, representation_1_occurrences, \
        representation_2_correct_answers, \
        representation_2_occurrences)

```

```

1 representations_statistics_all = [0, 0, 0, 0]
2 for sample_number in [0, 164, 177]:
3     # Retrieve the information (statistics) regarding data considered
4     statistics = questionStatistics(sample_number,4)
5     representations_statistics_all[0] += statistics[0]
6     representations_statistics_all[1] += statistics[1]
7     representations_statistics_all[2] += statistics[2]
8     representations_statistics_all[3] += statistics[3]

```

```

1 # Function for plotting statistics
2 def plotExpComparison(rep_statistics):
3
4     fig_explanations_comparison = make_subplots(rows=1, cols=2, specs=[[{"type": "\
        pie"}, {"type": "pie"}]])
5
6     accuracy_1 = 0.0
7     accuracy_2 = 0.0
8
9     if rep_statistics[0] > 0:
10        accuracy_1 = round((rep_statistics[0] / rep_statistics[1]),3)
11
12    if rep_statistics[2] > 0:
13        accuracy_2 = round((rep_statistics[2] / rep_statistics[3]),3)
14
15    display(Markdown("""
16    * Prediction Accuracy on Explanation 1: {}
17    * Prediction Accuracy on Explanation 2: {}""".format(accuracy_1, accuracy_2)))
18
19    # Plots of the results
20
21    # Accuracy Plots
22    fig_explanations_comparison.add_trace(go.Pie(
23        values=[rep_statistics[0],rep_statistics[1] - rep_statistics[0]],

```

```

24     labels=["Correct Answers", "Uncorrect Answers"],
25     hole=.5,
26     domain=dict(x=[0, 0.5]),
27     name="Explanation 1"),
28     row=1, col=1)
29
30 fig_explanations_comparison.add_trace(go.Pie(
31     values=[rep_statistics[2],rep_statistics[3] - rep_statistics[2]],
32     labels=["Correct Answers", "Uncorrect Answers"],
33     hole=.5,
34     domain=dict(x=[0.5, 1.0]),
35     name="Explanation 2"),
36     row=1, col=2)
37
38 fig_explanations_comparison.update_layout(height=400, width=1000, title_text="\
39     Prediction Accuracy of the \
40     Participants: Explanation 1 vs \
41     Explanation 2")
42
43 display(fig_explanations_comparison)

```

As result of running the previous code, we can see the following pie charts.

Figure 36: Comparison of Effectiveness of Explanations in the second user study.

Then, we explained participants how our operational framework works with a brief presentation (covering all related steps in the Planning and Execution stages: from generating the questionnaires until analyzing the collected results). Participants had 10 minutes to explore the framework and then had to answer to three general questions regarding understandability, confidence and predictability issues. Each answer was collected in a 5-point Likert scale (“Strongly agree”, “Agree”, “Neither agree nor disagree”, “Disagree”, “Strongly disagree”):

- S1: “The provided explanations helped me understand how decision trees work”.
- S2: “I am confident in the tool. I think it works well”.
- S3: “The outputs of the tool are very predictable”.

After running the following code, you can see additional pie charts which depict the collected data.

```

1 participant_satisfaction_understandability = ['Strongly agree', 'Agree', 'Neither \
agree nor disagree', 'Disagree', '\
Strongly disagree']
2 participant_satisfaction_confidence = ['Strongly agree', 'Agree', 'Neither agree nor\
disagree', 'Disagree', 'Strongly \
disagree']
3 participant_satisfaction_predictability = ['Strongly agree', 'Agree', 'Neither agree\
nor disagree', 'Disagree', 'Strongly \
disagree']

```

```

1 participant_satisfaction_understandability_values = []
2 counter = 0
3 for i,label in zip(range(1, len(participant_satisfaction_understandability) + 1),\
participant_satisfaction_understandability\
.copy()):
4     counter = int(data[['S1-understandability']].eq(str(i)).sum().values)
5     if counter != 0:
6         participant_satisfaction_understandability_values.append(counter)
7     else:
8         participant_satisfaction_understandability.remove(label)
9
10 participant_satisfaction_confidence_values = []
11 counter = 0
12 for i,label in zip(range(1, len(participant_satisfaction_confidence) + 1),\
participant_satisfaction_confidence.copy\
()):
13     counter = int(data[['S2-confidence']].eq(str(i)).sum().values)
14     if counter != 0:
15         participant_satisfaction_confidence_values.append(counter)
16     else:
17         participant_satisfaction_confidence.remove(label)
18
19 participant_satisfaction_predictability_values = []
20 counter = 0
21 for i,label in zip(range(1, len(participant_satisfaction_predictability) + 1),\
participant_satisfaction_predictability.\
copy()):
22     counter = int(data[['S3-predictability']].eq(str(i)).sum().values)
23     if counter != 0:
24         participant_satisfaction_predictability_values.append(counter)
25     else:
26         participant_satisfaction_predictability.remove(label)

```

```

1 pie_5 = go.Figure(data=[go.Pie(
2     name = 'The provided explanations helped me understand how decision trees work',
3     labels = participant_satisfaction_understandability,
4     values = participant_satisfaction_understandability_values,
5     hole=.5
6 )])
7 pie_5.update_layout(
8     height=400,
9     width=1000,
10    title_text="The provided explanations helped me understand how decision trees \
11                work"

```

The provided explanations helped me understand how decision trees work

Figure 37: Users' satisfaction with the utility of the operational framework.

```

1 pie_6 = go.Figure(data=[go.Pie(
2     name = 'I am confident in the tool. I think it works well',
3     labels = participant_satisfaction_confidence,
4     values = participant_satisfaction_confidence_values,
5     hole=.5
6 )])
7 pie_6.update_layout(
8     height=400,
9     width=1000,
10    title_text="I am confident in the tool. I think it works well"
11 )

```

I am confident in the tool. I think it works well

Figure 38: Users' confidence in the operational framework.

```

1 pie_7 = go.Figure(data=[go.Pie(
2     name = 'The outputs of the tool are predictable',
3     labels = participant_satisfaction_predictability,
4     values = participant_satisfaction_predictability_values,
5     hole=.5
6 )])
7 pie_7.update_layout(
8     height=400,
9     width=1000,
10    title_text="The outputs of the tool are predictable"
11 )

```


Figure 39: Users' satisfaction with the predictability of the operational framework.

In light of previous results, we can conclude that most participants were satisfied with our operational framework for guiding human evaluation in Explainable and Trustworthy AI.

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